

Normative modelling as a paradigm of the formatting power of mathematics: Educational value and learning environments

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Mathematical modelling can be differentiated into a descriptive and a normative prototype: While the first reproduces realistic phenomena by means of mathematics, the second represents the use of mathematics in order to shape reality. The describing function of mathematics nourishes common beliefs of mathematics, whereas normative modelling leads to the discovery of characteristics as subjectivity, ambiguity and dependency on human influence. The educational value of teaching normative modelling has several aspects: broadening the understanding of mathematical modelling, promoting citizen empowerment and initiating a reflection about the role of mathematics in society. This potential is illustrated by suggesting concrete learning environments that enable the discovery of normative modelling in civic issues.

Citizen empowerment as motivation

Applied mathematics are only interesting and really indispensable for general knowledge, when real life examples illustrate the functioning of mathematical modelling (Winter, 1995, p. 38, translation by the authors).

The application of mathematics in various contexts is a necessary condition for its usefulness but is not a sufficient one for its educational value. Mathematical modelling as the act of correlating reality with mathematics is often taught in order to prove the presence of mathematics in everyday life. Exemplary context should not be limited to the objective that students can cope with this specific situation. Furthermore, it is indispensable from the perspective of promoting citizen empowerment that they discover how and wherefore mathematics is used and which impacts has this modelling for reality. More than being able to calculate their income tax, students should know the main determining decisions behind this tax model and not confuse this arbitrary variable setting with physical constants. This use of modelling represents a concrete paradigm for the formatting power of mathematics and is a motivation for an awareness rising: Recognising which aspects of a mathematical modelling in a socially relevant context can be changed and in which way reveals possible courses of action and enables a public debate on desirable transformations.

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This paper begins with the differentiation between a descriptive and a normative function of modelling. As shown afterwards, the latter dispose of important educational potential for a broader understanding of mathematical modelling as well as for its application in social, economic or political contexts. Finally, the design of exemplary learning environments gives the opportunity to discuss how normative modelling can be taught and what insights students have acquired in previous implementations.

Characterisation of normative modelling

Davis and Hersh (1986, p. 115) enumerate three functions of mathematics: descriptive, predictive and prescriptive. This enumeration can be complemented and transferred to models: There are models that describe, that predict, that prescribe and that explain (Henn, 2002, p. 6).

Figure 1: Scheme of descriptive modelling

Nevertheless, the first three can be summarised as the result of descriptive modelling as they have a certain approach in common: ‘Descriptive’ relates to the fact that all three models are based on a mathematisation of a real-life phenomenon (Fig. 1). The apple had fallen before Newton formulated his law of gravity. The Arctic Ice would have melted and would continue to melt even without a mathematical description or prediction. Freudenthal (1978) speaks of models as “after images” or “plaster cast” (p. 131). The mathematical modelling serves as a reproduction for a better processing, analysis and understanding of the original phenomenon. Consequently, the motivation of the descriptive mathematical modelling constitutes the following subcategories of descriptive, explanatory and predictive modelling.

Figure 2: Scheme of normative modelling (Pohlkamp & Heitzer, 2020b, p. 218)

In the case of normative modelling, mathematics is however used to design standards and rules in order to shape or even create reality (Fig. 2). Hence, the reference to formatting norms explains the denomination although the term prescriptive modelling would be a synonym (Greefrath & Vorhölter, 2016, p. 9). For further illustration of this type of modelling, Freudenthal (1978) uses the metaphor of the “knitting pattern” (p. 131), the comparison with playing rules is by experience particularly suitable for students. One example of the formatting power of normative modelling is the income taxes: You can only pay taxes, once a tax rate has been defined.

Nevertheless, such an example could contribute to misconceptions: Of course, a given tax rate also describes the amount due and a citizen can predict one’s tax debt with help of the mathematical function. The categorisation ‘descriptive vs. normative’ refers more to the intention of the original modelling process than to the handling of the resulted model. That is why we prefer to attribute these adjectives only to ‘modelling’ and normally not to ‘model’. Furthermore, this dichotomy is based on idealised prototypes. Often aspects of both types interfere in realistic contexts: In particular, the normative modelling of a tax rate is not totally independent from a descriptive report of individual and public finances: On the one hand everyone should still be able to live from the money remaining after taxes, on the other hand the state needs a certain amount to offer its services.

For the purpose of analysing mathematics (education) from a social and political perspective Skovsmose (1998) formulated “the thesis of the *formatting power of mathematics*: Social phenomena are structured and eventually constituted by mathematics” (p. 197, emphasis in original). Normative modelling may not be the only manifestation of the formatting power of mathematics, but it represents a paradigm making insightful foci accessible. In particular, the difference between applied mathematics in natural versus social sciences can be drawn. In addition, somebody is actively formulating or varying the conditions of social interaction during the process of normative modelling by using mathematics. In this context, the human influence on the formatting power becomes obvious. Even if mathematics should in general not be reduced to being a tool, the perspective on the modeller leads to a critical characterisation of the process itself. Normative modelling is not unambiguous, but subjective as well as debatable (Pohlkamp, 2020). Thus, other persons could get a totally different outcome depending on their modelling decision. In a democratic society there should not be one autocratic modeller, instead the modelling should be established on a social consensus, Davis speaks of a social contract:

The ‘contract’ metaphor is a useful phrase to designate the interplay between people and their mathematics and to make the point that mathematizations are the work of man, constructed according to human will (Davis, 1988, p. 12).

This reference to the Enlightenment indicates the educational value of sensitising to this use of mathematics: It makes a difference whether you deal with a descriptive or a normative modelling. In contrast to the laws of physics you can easily dispute and change some parameters in the model of the tax income. Even though we have used the same instance for normative modelling until now, other examples document the significance of mathematical

norms behind civic issues: the definition of poverty (Vohns, 2017, pp. 972–976), proportional representation, business valuation, allocation of resources, air pollution thresholds ...

Normative modelling constitutes a valuable instrument for precisising and analysing the way in which mathematics is used in the set-up of human society.

Educational value of normative modelling

Hereinafter, the educational value of discussing normative modelling with mathematic students will be outlined. For that matter, the understanding of education expressed here follows the German speaking tradition integrating “aspects of societal participation and active citizenship as important goals of formation” (Vohns, 2017, p. 970). Similarly, Apple (1992) differentiates between a functional and a critical mathematical literacy: The first comprises the skills needed to be well adapted for everyday life and to contribute to the economy; however, the latter includes in a broader understanding the ability to challenge the existing social order. In this regard, knowledge about normative modelling enables to understand the mathematical mechanisms behind certain social constructions. Even if many modellings are very complex, a reflection of exemplary authentic contexts offers a framework for a civic engagement: Participating in a public debate as future citizens means that students are able to name and question the relevant mathematical aspects and methods.

While modelling has been implemented as a mathematical competence in most curricula of German language, it can be shown that normative modelling remains a blind spot, because the definition of mathematical modelling is often restricted to a descriptive function. At the same time, analysing the formatting power of mathematics can easily be discussed with students via the modelling discourse. Moreover, studying normative modelling addresses specific sub-competencies of modelling. In the process of normative modelling the steps of mathematising, interpreting and validating (Greefrath & Vorhölter, 2016, p. 19) are crucial. Thereby, modellers take at first contestable decisions – is a fee fair if everyone pays the same absolute amount (e.g., broadcast license fee in Germany) in contrast to the same percentage (e.g., day-fines as sentence) or would it even be thinkable if richer persons paid relatively more (e.g., progressive income tax)? Then they can check the consequences of their premisses and decisions by measuring the effects in reality and by comparing alternative models. The multitude and arbitrariness of the way mathematics is used to shape reality become obvious. Certainly, ignoring the air resistance is a considerable human interference in formulating the formulas of free fall. But an experiment proceeds the modelling which results can be verified with empiric data. Yet in the normative case, there is no best approximation to the original phenomenon; neither is there a limitation whether the formula of the tax income should be based on a linear, a proportional or still exponential function.

Doing justice to the normative type when teaching modelling is tied to complementary learning targets. The general objective of *explaining the formatting power of mathematics by means of normative modelling* comprehends amongst others the following targets (Pohlkamp, 2020):

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1. *Exemplifying prototypic characteristics of normative modelling*

Discovering the abovementioned characteristics as ambiguity and subjectivity facilitates to deconstruct the myths about Mathematics that Hersch (1991) identified. This initiates a reflection of mathematics, its use and role in society as another positive impulse.

2. *Outlining premises, decisions and alternatives*

The task is to encourage critical minds. Confronted with supposedly completed models, a responsible citizen should be qualified to detect other options and especially be careful if they are being told that there is not an alternative.

3. *Judging normative modellings as well as the possibility of judgment*

While comparing different outcomes given the same cause for the normative modelling, students encounter the same challenges as during the modelling. As there cannot be a benchmark as exactness of reproduction, the choice of quality criteria is subjective and arbitrary as well. Whether a tax model is fair depends on your understanding of fairness.

The ideal long-term objective is *distinguishing descriptive and normative elements in authentic modellings* by taking into account that the prototypes rarely occur in purity. Due to the larger dissemination of descriptive modelling these learning targets express the plea that an examination of the normative type should be integrated in learning mathematics before a direct juxtaposition. Exposing the misconception of mathematics as a tool of neutral reproduction goes along with a search for decisions in so called descriptive modellings that are debatable and maybe biased.

There are good reasons to address basic knowledge and the ability of reflection rather than technical skills in order to empower citizens' participation in complex discourses (Fischer, 2012, pp. 13–14). Nevertheless, *constructing an own solution to realistic problems by retracing the process of normative modelling* is a deliberate approach. Thus, students are sensitised for the formatting power because they experience the variety of possible decisions. Whereas most citizen are consumers of models originated of a normative intention, the producers' standpoint is yet instructive according to the following analogy: Empirical psychological results of an online simulation have shown that once learners have produced fake news on their own, they are more critical when facing up misinformation afterwards (Roozenbeek & van der Linden, 2019).

In the same way that playing rules determine sportive and/or gaming activities, normative modelling contributes to a quantified regulation whenever a political, economic or interpersonal situation seem to call for it. Taking into consideration that paradigmatic applications emanate from social sciences, you can differentiate the perception of the position of mathematics in the canon of school subjects. Not only in a general perspective, but also for vocational preparation it is important that students round off their vision of mathematics traditionally associated within the STEM-disciplines. However, this can contribute to misconceptions. After a workshop introducing normative modelling one student formulated the lesson learned "Mathematics exists everywhere" (transl. by the

authors). This overregularisation of the existence of mathematics beyond natural science is a manifestation of an all-embracing jurisdiction of mathematics (Kollosche, 2017, p. 641).

But overall, learning targets around normative modelling can be linked to encouraging attitudes of a critical citizenship. It is a technique of domination when “producers of normative models like to behave as though their models were well-determined and unique” (Freudenthal, 1978, p. 135). Therefore, it is emancipatory for students to investigate the often hidden mechanism in the construction and functioning of the societal reality.

Insights within exemplary learning environments

Introducing normative modelling to students can take place on a fundamental level:

Mara calls for a taxi to the train station. Halfway, her friend Nele is joining her. The whole ride costs 12 euros. How should they split the costs? (Sjuts, 2009, p. 191, translation and adaption by the authors).

Apart from obvious answers – Mara pays 12 euros (she called for the taxi and didn't need to share the ride), each defrays 6 euros (each one reached her destination) – the following solutions surprise students the most: Mara pays 8 euros and Nele 4 euros (Mara travelled twice as far) vs. Mara contributes 9 euros and Nele 3 euros (Mara pays the first half distance on her own, while they are sharing the second one equally). In a mathematical argumentation most students do not expect such results revealing principal characteristics of normative modelling: ambiguity (several logical solutions without a calculation error), subjectivity (it is one's interest to pay the less possible) and the necessity of a debate (you can't agree to disagree as the taxi driver must be paid). As *pars pro toto* for questions of allocation, the citizen empowerment is pertinent: Not knowing the alternatives is a disadvantage for one of the girls. One constraint is however, that some students are not aware of the political dimension, a difference of one euro is too insignificant. The other consists in the simple calculation for which reason no modelling competencies are stimulated.

An appropriate context of retracing a complex modelling process with students is proportional representation; starting with discussing proportionality vs. integrity, students remodel different methods of apportionment and form an opinion about current reforms of the election system (Pohlkamp & Heitzer, 2020b). Exploring normative modelling can also be limited to vary parameters of a given model. When students define a tax income threshold in a digital visualisation and dynamically examine consequences, the arbitrariness of any decision becomes obvious (Pohlkamp & Heitzer 2020a, pp. 291–292). In face of the malleability within one model, critical insisting on the technical background of civic issues is worth it whereas references to mathematical argumentations are normally intended to conclude a public debate.

Analysing economic models is in particular educational because they appear more objective than political or social contexts. In fact, interest-calculation is part of most mathematics curricula without referring to its normativity. This topic is treated as an unalterable formula although anthropologically there has been a different view on interests forbidden or condemned by most religions.

Business valuation is another economic issue widely spread in media. An open activity would be to let students compare financial statement data from e.g., the *big five* tech companies. In order to nominate the most valuable company they have to select data they consider relevant, translate values of different unities in one point scale and to weigh these results. If intended, business vocabulary like the difference between revenue and profit can be familiarised for general knowledge. From the point of normative modelling, it is more important that students deduce the prototypical characteristics from their own procedure and reflect possible judgements by comparing the different models. Even if most models generated by students are far from realistic models, it arises a critical potential. In a try-out of this activity most of the students' models integrated the company's staff number and often prioritised it with a high weight. Verifying that the staff number is irrelevant in common authentic models leads as far as denouncing the role of human in capitalism.

Economic models are good examples that not only the choice of a model exhibits normativity, but also the choice of data within a model. The product of the number of a company's outstanding shares and the value of a share defines the market capitalisation, common referent for business valuation. Since the share value changes nearly daily, the day of reference is important information and the market capitalisation a volatile value. This relativises frequent headlines on which company (mostly one of the *big five*) is currently the most valuable.

An authentic and accessible other context to promote both modelling competencies and statistical literacy is to deal with real data about the Sea Ice (Fetterer et al., 2017). At first glance describing the past and predicting the future development of the surface via regression seem to be a classical descriptive modelling. Of course, this visualisation (Fig. 3) represents the conclusion of a students' activity to examine the data, but it is the moment when an analysis with respect to normative aspects becomes relevant. Taking a deeper look, it makes a huge difference on which statistical measure the model is based. Extrapolating from the surface maxima of the last years you could even claim that the change is marginal. Students reconstruct how climate change deniers would select data to support their messages devoid a detectable calculation error. The normativity lies on the one hand on the arbitrariness of the choice, on the other hand, the visualisation shapes how dramatic we perceive the described phenomenon. This contradicts the common belief that the description by mathematical means is *per se* neutral. Such a modelling perspective cannot only be applied to the data processing, but also to the collection of data: By measuring the surface it must be distinguished between the area and the extent of the sea ice. Further critical questions could for example extend to: the difference between surface and volume (balancing between the effort of data collecting or rather of modelling and the accuracy of the outcome), the assumption of a linear regression (and its restrained validity on a larger interval), the neglect of aggravating aspects (effects of the climate crises are interdependent). All are consequences of human decisions in the data-based modelling process. Provided that both prototypes of modelling are familiar, the examination of this context initiates the discovery of a hybrid form next to learning of the climate crisis.

Figure 3: Modelling the development of the sea ice surface

These different teaching ideas give an example in which form and by means of which issues normative modelling can be concretised for students. Learning in the context is always tied to the meta theme of normative modelling embodying the formatting power of mathematics and the human influence on its use.

Concluding reflection with respect to common beliefs about mathematics

In extracurricular workshops the functionality of almost all learning environments mentioned above could be tested, usually they were combined with a lesson about the normative modelling of apportionment methods. On the basis of written answers by the students (n=67), the learning results could be contrasted with the primary targets. When asked to “explain normative modelling in [their] own words” students are able to summarise principal characteristics of normative modelling as ambiguity, shaping of rules/reality, subjectivity. Some aspects are illustrated by their own metaphors (e.g., set screw, stencil) or examples (e.g., demarcation between countries, wage increase). However, the following statements are typical for a certain unease (transl. by the authors):

Mathematics is used to develop a human-made model. The set screws can be selected freely. This is not natural.

[Normative Modelling is the] mathematical background in reality and the penury of math for describing situations.

The reflection of normative modelling comes into conflict with internalised beliefs about mathematics. The first quotation insists that mathematics is an invariable system that humans aren’t allowed to change. In the second one, although the limits of mathematics are recognised (“penury”), the domination of the describing function of mathematics persists.

Both wordings have in common that mathematics is first and foremost associated with a neutral tool. In addition, there is a tendency to reduce mathematics to calculation in order to rescue the concept of unity and objectivity and to blame the context for any unexpected and irritating effects:

[Normative Modelling is a] context interfering into mathematics.

Overall, students can explain normative modelling, its mode of operation and its significance and they wish to learn further about it. Despite this positive evaluation, students attribute traits to mathematics that are quite antithetical to normative modelling. This tension revealed via the learning environments initiates a critical reflection about the formatting power of normative modelling that has been pointed out by most of the students:

One determines something by means of mathematics in order to apply it to reality.

Even if a certain vision of mathematics seems to be deep-seated, normative modelling has shown to be an opportunity to discuss a use of mathematics that is relatively unknown and yet so relevant: Sensitised to the normative use of mathematics, citizens are no longer misled by the idea that mathematical arguments in political and social context are neutral and irrevocable. Only the knowledge about this changeability enables a reaction to social orders based on mathematisations: If one cannot fight descriptively modeled natural laws, one can fight social constructs as products of rather arbitrary normative modeling. The latter are also omnipresent in the human world:

We are born into a world with so many instances of prescriptive [normative] mathematics in place that we are hardly aware of them, and, once they are pointed out, we can hardly imagine the world working without them. (Davis & Hersh, 1986, p. 120)

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